

ECONOMY

THE IMPACT OF PUBLIC EDUCATION AND HEALTHCARE EXPENDITURES ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN UZBEKISTAN

Niyazmetov M.,

Rector of International School of Finance Technology and Science (ISFT)

Ostonokulov A.

DSc., Professor of International School of Finance Technology and Science (ISFT)

Abstract

This study investigates the intricate relationship between government expenditures, focusing on education and healthcare, and their impact on economic growth in Uzbekistan. Using data spanning from 2000 to 2022, we employ an OLS regression model to analyze the dynamics of these factors alongside gross capital formation and inflation rates. Our findings reveal positive correlations between government spending on education and healthcare, economic growth, and capital formation, emphasizing the importance of investments in human capital and infrastructure for sustained economic development. Conversely, inflation rates exhibit a negative association with economic growth. These insights provide valuable guidance for Uzbekistan's economists seeking to foster economic growth while ensuring the well-being of its citizens.

Keywords: government expenditures, education, healthcare, economic growth, gross capital formation, inflation, OLS regression analysis, human capital, fiscal policy.

INTRODUCTION

Economists have long recognized the pivotal role of human capital in driving economic growth, as evidenced by the seminal works of scholars such as Schultz (1961), Becker (1964), Uzawa (1965), and Rosen (1976). Schultz argued that investments in human capital, including expenditures on education and health, constitute a significant driver behind the increase in real earnings per worker. Becker (1964) expounded on this notion, asserting that investments in human capital enhance an individual's productivity and income. The core concept underlying these assertions is that a highly educated and healthier workforce is inherently more productive, thereby contributing to economic growth. Subsequent research has continued to underscore the critical role of human capital in explaining variations in economic growth among countries, with seminal contributions by economists like Lucas (1988), Mulligan and Sala-i-Martin (1993), and Barro and Sala-i-Martin (1995).

Empirical studies have lent empirical support to the idea that human capital is crucial for sustained economic growth, with notable contributions from scholars like Romer (1986), Barro (1991), Levine and Renelt (1992), Mankiw et al. (1992), Barro and Lee (1993), Bassanini and Scarpetta (2001), Krueger and Lindahl (2001), and Baldacci et al. (2004). However, it is worth noting that some studies have surprisingly found a weak association between human capital and growth or even negative effects (see Benhabib and Spiegel, 1994; Bils and Klenow, 2000; Caselli et al., 1996; Islam, 1995; Knight et al., 1993; Pritchett, 1996). Several factors could explain the lack of a robust association between human capital and growth, including variations in model specifications and the inclusion or exclusion of specific control variables, as emphasized by Levine and Renelt (1992).

Although health has been acknowledged as a fundamental component of human capital, much of the

economic growth and development literature has traditionally limited the concept of human capital to education (see e.g., Schultz, 1961; Bloom et al., 2001; Barro, 2013). However, it is crucial to recognize that governments play a pivotal role in investing in both basic education and primary healthcare in most countries. Despite this, the empirical evidence regarding the growth impacts of these investments remains mixed and inconclusive.

Uzbekistan, with its diverse and youthful population, is well-poised to leverage the potential of human capital development. The government of Uzbekistan has placed education and healthcare at the core of its national development agenda, recognizing that an educated and healthy workforce is a key driver of economic growth and prosperity. The nation's leadership has embarked on ambitious reforms aimed at improving the quality of education, expanding access to healthcare services, and fostering innovation within these sectors.

However, as Uzbekistan navigates its unique path of economic transformation and openness, it faces specific challenges and opportunities. Historical legacies, cultural diversity, and the evolving landscape of technology all play a crucial role in shaping the effectiveness of public education and healthcare expenditures in driving economic growth. It is within this context that we seek to explore the multifaceted dimensions of the relationship between investments in education, healthcare, and economic growth in Uzbekistan.

This article will offer an in-depth analysis of the impact of public education and healthcare expenditures on Uzbekistan's economic growth, considering the evolving dynamics within the nation's social and economic fabric. By examining both theoretical frameworks and empirical evidence, we aim to provide valuable insights for policymakers, researchers, and stakeholders invested in Uzbekistan's pursuit of sustained economic growth, improved living standards, and a brighter future for its citizens.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Education and healthcare expenditures have long been recognized as vital investments in human capital and have been extensively studied in the context of economic growth. The literature on this subject highlights various mechanisms through which education can influence economic growth. These mechanisms include enhancing workforce efficiency, reducing inequality, promoting better health, lowering fertility rates, creating an environment conducive to good governance, and increasing a nation's knowledge and innovative capacity (Aghion et al., 1999; Castelló-Climent and Doménech, 2008; Lipset, 1960; Glaeser et al., 2004; Castelló-Climent, 2008; Benhabib and Spiegel, 1994; Hanushek and Woessmann, 2008).

Numerous theoretical papers have explored the relationship between government education expenditure and economic growth. Among these studies, Glomm and Ravikumar (1992, 1997, 1998), Eckstein and Zilcha (1994), Zhang (1996), Kaganovich and Zilcha (1999), Cassou and Lansing (2001), Benabou (2002), Blankeanu (2005), and Wigger (2004) have examined the implications of education on growth and income inequality, the role of education subsidization, and the impact of schooling on economic growth. For instance, Glomm and Ravikumar (1992) found that public education can lead to higher per capita incomes when initial income inequality is high in a generational model. Zhang (1996) concluded that education subsidization stimulates growth and mitigates welfare losses due to human capital externalities.

However, empirical evidence regarding the relationship between government education expenditure and economic growth has yielded mixed results. While Zhang and Casagrande (1998), Barro and Sala-i-Martin (1995), and Baldacci et al. (2008) have found a positive association between government education expenditure and economic growth, Easterly and Rebelo (1993) identified this positive relationship only under certain specifications. Devarajan et al. (1996), Landau (1986), Levine and Renelt (1992), and Keller (2006) found no significant connection between the two.

Turning to the realm of healthcare, one direct avenue through which health impacts economic growth is by enhancing workforce productivity. Grossman (1972) treated health as a capital good, arguing that investments in health capital reduce time lost to illness, thereby increasing productivity. Jack (1999) emphasized the relationship between human capital investments and workforce capabilities, while Strauss and Thomas (1998) presented evidence supporting the link between productivity and health. Bloom and Canning (2000) pointed out that healthy populations tend to exhibit better physical and mental capabilities, contributing to increased productivity.

Health can also indirectly influence economic growth by affecting education performance. Good health is associated with higher levels of schooling and better educational outcomes. Barro (1996) found that improved health indicators create an incentive for investing in education. Furthermore, health-related issues can lead to reduced labor productivity and fewer years

of schooling for children, especially when parents suffer from chronic illnesses.

Additionally, health can make development more achievable by addressing economic hindrances caused by unfavorable health conditions. Sorkin (1977) suggested that major health programs could stimulate development in areas where economic activity is impeded by health-related issues. This idea aligns with the perspective of Bryant (1969), who argued that improving health and healthcare services can enhance economic development and social progress in the developing world.

Moreover, health has an impact on wealth and income, with higher levels of individual wealth contributing to economic growth. Lillard and Weiss (1997) and Smith (1998) established a connection between health and future income, while improved health outcomes positively affect education performance, leading to increased productivity and, subsequently, higher wealth and income.

Compared to the empirical literature on education's effect on growth, the research on the impact of health on growth remains relatively limited. Jamison et al. (2004) found that improvements in health accounted for approximately one-tenth of economic growth, using data from both developed and developing countries from 1965 to 1990. Other studies, such as Rivera and Currais (1999a, 1999b) and Beraldo et al. (2005), reported statistically significant effects of health expenditures on growth when considering OECD countries. However, most studies examining government health expenditure have found either a negative or statistically insignificant effect on economic growth, with Cooray (2009) being an exception, supporting a positive and significant impact of government health expenditure on growth.

Healthcare and education are pivotal in shaping the socio-economic development of a country. A study examining the dynamic effect of healthcare and education expenditure on economic growth in Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) countries found a robust long-run co-integrating relationship between these expenditures and economic growth (Wahab, Kefeli, & Hashim, 2018). This study highlighted that healthy and well-educated populations significantly contribute to the economic advancement of a country. In the short run, healthcare expenditure per capita had a significant impact on economic growth, while education expenditure and research and development had an insignificant impact.

In a related study, the causal relationship between public social expenditure (education and health) and economic growth in Nigeria was examined for the period 1990 to 2009 (Ayuba, 2011). Applying the Vector Error Correction (VEC) Model Based Causality, the study found a unidirectional causality running from economic growth to health expenditure, supporting Wagner's Law. The study recommended increased budgetary allocations for education and health sectors and exploring other financing sources to enhance economic growth.

A study conducted in Ghana examined the effect of public health expenditure on health status, using data

from 1990 to 2012 (Boachie & Ramu, 2016). The study used infant mortality rate as an output variable and found that public health expenditure, along with literacy levels, were negatively related to infant mortality rate. This suggests that increased public health spending and improved literacy/education can significantly improve health status, which in turn, can have a positive impact on economic growth.

DATA COLLECTION AND METHODOLOGY

In this study, we undertake an empirical analysis to investigate the influence of state budget allocations directed towards education and healthcare expenditures on economic growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan. To facilitate this analysis, we employ a comprehensive dataset encompassing information from various sources, including the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Statistics Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and supplementary data from the World Bank. The dataset encompasses a substantial temporal span, ranging from the year 2000 to 2022, thus offering a comprehensive overview of long-term trends and dynamics.

To empirically assess the relationship between state budget allocations for education and healthcare and their impact on economic growth in Uzbekistan, we employ the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression model. OLS is a widely recognized and widely used econometric technique that enables the estimation of linear relationships between variables. In the context of this study, the OLS model allows us to determine the extent to which government expenditures in education and healthcare contribute to variations in economic growth over the specified period.

Our model formulation considers economic growth as the dependent variable, while the independent variables encompass government expenditures on education and healthcare. By controlling for potential confounding factors and employing rigorous econometric techniques, we aim to elucidate the specific impact of public investments in education and healthcare on Uzbekistan's economic growth trajectory.

Econometric Model Specification

The proposed econometric model can be specified as follows:

$$\text{GDPGrowthRate}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \times \text{EduExp}_t + \beta_2 \times \text{HealthExp}_t + \beta_3 \times \text{CapForm}_t + \beta_4 \times \text{Inflation}_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Where:

GDPGrowthRate_t: Economic Growth (GDP Growth Rate) at time t.

EduExp_t: Government Expenditure on Education (% of GDP) at time t.

HealthExp_t: Government Expenditure on Healthcare (% of GDP) at time t.

CapForm_t: Gross Capital Formation (% of GDP) at time t.

Inflation_t: Inflation Rate (%) at time t.

B₀: Intercept term.

β1, β2, β3, β4: Coefficients for the respective independent variables.

ε_t: Error term at time t.

Economic Growth (GDP Growth Rate): This is the dependent variable, representing the annual percentage change in Uzbekistan's GDP. It's a measure of the overall economic performance of the country.

Government Expenditure on Education (% of GDP): This independent variable reflects the government's investment in the education sector. A higher percentage suggests a greater emphasis on education, which can influence economic growth through improved human capital.

Government Expenditure on Healthcare (% of GDP): This variable indicates the government's spending on healthcare. Adequate healthcare spending can improve the general health of the workforce, potentially leading to increased productivity and economic growth.

Gross Capital Formation (% of GDP): This represents investments in infrastructure and productive capacity. Higher values suggest more significant investments, which can directly contribute to economic growth by increasing the country's productive capacity.

Inflation Rate (%): The inflation rate is a measure of the rate at which prices for goods and services are rising. High inflation rates can have a negative impact on economic growth by reducing the purchasing power of consumers and increasing uncertainty for investors.

Model Usage and Interpretation

This model can be used to analyze how changes in each of these independent variables are associated with changes in Uzbekistan's economic growth rate. The coefficients (β1, β2, β3, β4) will indicate the direction and magnitude of the relationship between each independent variable and the GDP growth rate. A positive coefficient suggests that an increase in the variable is associated with an increase in economic growth, while a negative coefficient indicates the opposite.

Table 1.

Correlation Matrix

	Economic Growth	Gov. Education (% of GDP)	Gov. Healthcare (% of GDP)	Gross Capital Formation (% of GDP)	Inflation Rate (%)
Economic Growth	1.0	0.7	0.5	0.6	-0.4
Gov. Education (% of GDP)	0.7	1.0	0.4	0.3	-0.2
Gov. Healthcare (% of GDP)	0.5	0.4	1.0	0.2	-0.1
Gross Capital Formation (% of GDP)	0.6	0.3	0.2	1.0	-0.3
Inflation Rate (%)	-0.4	-0.2	-0.1	-0.3	1.0

Source: Developed by the authors

1. Economic Growth and Government Expenditure on Education and Healthcare: There are positive correlations between economic growth and government expenditure on education (0.7) and healthcare (0.5). This suggests that higher investments in these sectors are associated with better economic growth. This could be due to improved human capital and a healthier workforce enhancing productivity and thus contributing to GDP growth.

2. Economic Growth and Gross Capital Formation: The correlation coefficient of 0.6 indicates a positive relationship between economic growth and gross capital formation. This is intuitive, as investments in infrastructure and capital assets are critical drivers of

economic activity, leading to an increase in the productive capacity of the economy.

3. Economic Growth and Inflation Rate: There is a negative correlation (-0.4) between economic growth and the inflation rate. This could imply that higher inflation rates potentially harm economic growth, possibly due to reduced consumer purchasing power and increased uncertainty for investors.

4. Inter-correlations among Independent Variables: The correlations among the independent variables themselves, such as government expenditure on education and healthcare, are relatively moderate. This indicates that while these variables are related, they retain a level of independence in their impact on economic growth.

Table 2.

OLS regression results					
Variable	Coefficients	Standard Error	t-Statistic	P-Value	Sig
β_0	2.150	0.450	4.778	0.001	***
Gov. Education (% of GDP)	0.912	0.210	4.343	0.002	***
Gov. Healthcare (% of GDP)	0.485	0.183	2.650	0.025	**
Gross Capital Formation (% of GDP)	1.230	0.312	3.946	0.004	***
Inflation Rate (%)	-0.560	0.215	-2.604	0.027	**

Source: Developed by the authors

Discussion on OLS Regression Results

The OLS regression results provide insightful information about the impact of various independent variables on Economic Growth (GDP Growth Rate) in Uzbekistan.

Intercept (β_0): The intercept coefficient of 2.150, significant at the 0.1% level (***), suggests a baseline level of GDP growth. This baseline represents the expected value of GDP growth when all other independent variables are zero. The high significance of the intercept indicates that factors not included in the model might also be influencing economic growth.

Government Expenditure on Education (% of GDP): The coefficient of 0.912, significant at the 0.1% level (***), suggests a strong positive impact of education expenditure on economic growth. This implies that for each percentage increase in government expenditure on education as a proportion of GDP, the economic growth rate increases by approximately 0.912%, holding other factors constant. This underscores the importance of educational investment in fostering economic growth, likely through the development of human capital.

Government Expenditure on Healthcare (% of GDP): With a coefficient of 0.485, significant at the 5% level (**), healthcare expenditure also positively impacts economic growth, though its effect is less pronounced compared to education. This reflects the beneficial impact of health expenditure on workforce productivity and overall economic health.

Gross Capital Formation (% of GDP): The coefficient of 1.230, significant at the 0.1% level (***), indicates a substantial positive relationship with economic growth. This suggests that investments in infrastructure and capital assets are crucial drivers of economic growth, as they increase the productive capacity of the economy.

Inflation Rate (%): The coefficient of -0.560, significant at the 5% level (**), shows a negative impact on economic growth. This indicates that higher inflation rates tend to reduce the economic growth rate. The negative relationship could be attributed to inflation's tendency to erode purchasing power and introduce uncertainty in the economy.

The model demonstrates a strong fit, as indicated by the high R-squared value (0.782). This suggests that a significant portion of the variability in Uzbekistan's economic growth is explained by these variables. The results highlight the critical role of government spending in education and healthcare, and gross capital formation in driving economic growth. Conversely, the negative impact of inflation underscores the need for effective monetary policies to stabilize prices and sustain growth.

CONCLUSION

In this comprehensive analysis, we have explored the intricate relationship between government expenditures on education and healthcare, alongside various other economic factors, and their influence on the economic growth trajectory of Uzbekistan. Our investigation has shed light on several crucial insights that can guide policymakers and stakeholders in the pursuit of sustainable economic development.

First and foremost, our findings underscore the pivotal role of education as a catalyst for economic growth. The positive correlation between government expenditure on education as a percentage of GDP and economic growth indicates that investments in the education sector are associated with higher GDP growth rates. This alignment suggests that a well-educated workforce can significantly contribute to the country's economic advancement. Therefore, it is imperative for Uzbekistan's government to continue prioritizing edu-

cation and allocate adequate resources to enhance educational infrastructure, curriculum development, and overall educational quality.

Similarly, our analysis reveals a positive correlation between government healthcare expenditure as a percentage of GDP and economic growth. This finding suggests that investments in healthcare services can contribute positively to economic growth. A healthy population is more productive, resulting in improved labor force participation and efficiency. Thus, it is crucial for Uzbekistan to sustain and potentially increase investments in healthcare to ensure the well-being of its citizens while fostering economic growth.

Furthermore, our model considers additional factors that influence economic growth. Gross capital formation, representing investments in fixed assets, exhibits a positive correlation with economic growth. This underscores the importance of both public and private sector investments in infrastructure and productive capacity for economic development.

Conversely, the inflation rate displays a moderate negative correlation with economic growth. This finding underscores the significance of maintaining price stability and controlling inflation, as high inflation rates can hinder economic growth by eroding purchasing power and causing uncertainty in the economy.

In conclusion, our analysis demonstrates that a holistic approach to economic development in Uzbekistan involves a multifaceted strategy. Prioritizing education and healthcare expenditures, alongside prudent fiscal management to control inflation, can foster economic growth. Additionally, investments in capital formation are essential for creating a conducive environment for economic expansion.

It is crucial for Uzbekistan's economists to consider these insights when formulating economic and fiscal policies. By strategically allocating resources to education, healthcare, and infrastructure while maintaining price stability, Uzbekistan can pave the way for sustained and inclusive economic growth, ultimately improving the standard of living for its citizens and positioning itself as a dynamic and resilient economy on the global stage.

References

1. Aghion, P., Caroli, E., & Garcia-Peñalosa, C. (1999). Inequality and Economic Growth: The Perspective of the New Growth Theories. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 37(4), 1615-1660.
2. Ayuba, A. J. (2011). The Relationship between Public Social Expenditure and Economic Growth in Nigeria: An Empirical Analysis.
3. Baldacci, E., Clements, B., Gupta, S., & Cui, Q. (2004). Social Spending, Human Capital, and Growth in Developing Countries: Implications for Achieving the MDGs. *International Monetary Fund*.
4. Barro, R. J. (1991). Economic Growth in a Cross Section of Countries. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 106(2), 407-443.
5. Barro, R. J. (1996). Health and Economic Growth. *Harvard Center for Population and Development Studies Working Paper*, 96(1).
6. Barro, R. J. (2013). Health and Economic Growth. *Annals of Economics and Finance*, 14(2), 329-366.
7. Barro, R. J., & Lee, J. W. (1993). International Comparisons of Educational Attainment. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 32(3), 363-394.
8. Barro, R. J., & Sala-i-Martin, X. (1995). *Economic Growth*. McGraw-Hill.
9. Bassanini, A., & Scarpetta, S. (2001). The Driving Forces of Economic Growth: Panel Data Evidence for the OECD Countries. *OECD Economic Studies*, 33(1), 9-56.
10. Becker, G. S. (1964). *Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis, with Special Reference to Education*. National Bureau of Economic Research.
11. Benhabib, J., & Spiegel, M. M. (1994). The Role of Human Capital in Economic Development: Evidence from Aggregate Cross-Country Data. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 34(2), 143-173.
12. Benhabib, J., & Spiegel, M. M. (1994). The Role of Human Capital in Economic Development: Evidence from Aggregate Cross-Country Data. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 34(2), 143-173.
13. Beraldo, S., Montolio, D., & Turati, G. (2005). Health Expenditure and Income in the United States. *Empirical Economics*, 30(4), 855-880.
14. Bils, M. J., & Klenow, P. J. (2000). Does Schooling Cause Growth? *The American Economic Review*, 90(5), 1160-1183.
15. Bloom, D. E., & Canning, D. (2000). The Health and Wealth of Nations. *Science*, 287(5456), 1207-1209.
16. Bloom, D. E., Canning, D., & Sevilla, J. (2001). The Effect of Health on Economic Growth: A Production Function Approach. *World Development*, 32(1), 1-13.
17. Boachie, M., & Ramu, K. (2016). Effect of public health expenditure on health status in Ghana. *International Journal of Health*, 4(1). DOI: 10.14419/IJH.V4I1.5794.
18. Bryant, J. (1969). Health as an Economic Variable. *The American Economic Review*, 59(2), 251-259.
19. Caselli, F., Esquivel, G., & Lefort, F. (1996). Reopening the Convergence Debate: A New Look at Cross-Country Growth Empirics. *Journal of Economic Growth*, 1(3), 363-389.
20. Castelló-Climent, A. (2008). On the Distribution of Education and Democracy. *Journal of Development Economics*, 87(2), 179-190.
21. Castelló-Climent, A., & Doménech, R. (2008). Human Capital Inequality, Life Expectancy and Economic Growth. *The Economic Journal*, 118(528), 653-677.
22. Cooray, A. (2009). Government Health Expenditure and Economic Growth: A Federated States of Micronesia Case Study. *Applied Economics Letters*, 16(11), 1125-1129.
23. Glaeser, E. L., La Porta, R., Lopez-de-Silanes, F., & Shleifer, A. (2004). Do Institutions Cause Growth? *Journal of Economic Growth*, 9(3), 271-303.

24. Glomm, G., & Ravikumar, B. (1992). Public versus Private Investment in Human Capital: Endogenous Growth and Income Inequality. *Journal of Political Economy*, 100(4), 818-834.
25. Grossman, M. (1972). On the Concept of Health Capital and the Demand for Health. *Journal of Political Economy*, 80(2), 223-255.
26. Hanushek, E. A., & Woessmann, L. (2008). The Role of Cognitive Skills in Economic Development. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 46(3), 607-668.
27. Islam, N. (1995). Growth Empirics: A Panel Data Approach. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 110(4), 1127-1170.
28. Jack, W. (1999). Education and Labour Productivity in Zambia. World Bank.
29. Jamison, D. T., Lau, L. J., Wang, J. A., & World Bank. (2004). Health's Contribution to Economic Growth in an Environment of Partially Endogenous Technical Progress. In *Disease Control Priorities in Developing Countries* (2nd ed.).
30. Knight, J., Loayza, N., & Villanueva, D. (1993). Testing the Neoclassical Theory of Economic Growth: A Panel Data Approach. *IMF Staff Papers*, 40(3), 512-541.
31. Krueger, A. B., & Lindahl, M. (2001). Education for Growth: Why and for Whom? *Journal of Economic Literature*, 39(4), 1101-1136.
32. Levine, R., & Renelt, D. (1992). A Sensitivity Analysis of Cross-Country Growth Regressions. *The American Economic Review*, 82(4), 942-963.
33. Lillard, L. A., & Weiss, Y. (1997). Uncertain Health and Survival: Effects on End-of-Life Consumption. *Journal of Business & Economic Statistics*, 15(2), 254-268.
34. Lipset, S. M. (1960). *Political Man: The Social Bases of Politics*. Doubleday.
35. Lucas, R. E. (1988). On the Mechanics of Economic Development. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 22(1), 3-42.
36. Mankiw, N. G., Romer, D., & Weil, D. N. (1992). A Contribution to the Empirics of Economic Growth. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 107(2), 407-437.
37. Mulligan, C. B., & Sala-i-Martin, X. (1993). Transfers, Social Safety Nets, and Economic Growth. *IMF Staff Papers*, 40(4), 897-922.
38. Pritchett, L. (1996). Measuring Outcomes of Schooling. *The World Bank Research Observer*, 11(1), 37-61.
39. Rivera, B., & Currais, L. (1999a). A New Approach to the Theory of Health Production. *Journal of Health Economics*, 18(2), 161-178.
40. Rivera, B., & Currais, L. (1999b). Health Expenditure and Economic Growth. *Applied Economics Letters*, 6(11), 761-763.
41. Romer, P. M. (1986). Increasing Returns and Long-Run Growth. *Journal of Political Economy*, 94(5), 1002-1037.
42. Rosen, S. (1976). A Theory of Life Earnings. *Journal of Political Economy*, 84(4), S45-S67.
43. Schultz, T. W. (1961). Investment in Human Capital. *The American Economic Review*, 51(1), 1-17.
44. Smith, J. P. (1998). Socioeconomic Status and Health. *The American Economic Review*, 88(2), 192-196.
45. Sorkin, A. L. (1977). The Health Transition: Theoretical Models and Prospects for Its Application. In *Health Policy and Practice in Economic Development* (pp. 169-201). University of Chicago Press.
46. Strauss, J., & Thomas, D. (1998). Health, Nutrition, and Economic Development. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 36(2), 766-817.
47. Uzawa, H. (1965). Optimal Technical Change in an Aggregative Model of Economic Growth. *International Economic Review*, 6(1), 18-31.
48. Wahab, A., Kefeli, Z., & Hashim, N. (2018). Investigating The Dynamic Effect of Healthcare Expenditure and Education Expenditure On Economic Growth in Organisation of Islamic Countries (OIC).
49. Zhang, J. (1996). The Effects of Public Investment on Private Investment Behavior: Evidence from the Panel Data on Chinese Provinces. *Journal of Comparative Economics*, 22(3), 292-312.